

Epiphany in social communication

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Christmas is a time of illusion, sharing, and desire for change towards better days because hope is born. For Catholics and people of other faiths, December is a time of solidarity and expressions of kindness where the best in people is shown. Forgiveness characterises most celebrations. For this reason, there is also a longing for the spirit of each December to last every month.

But the illusion of communicating the positive is cut short after the holiday. Doom and conflict, often caused by the absence of dialogue, are in the headlines. Good news, ingenious solutions and new possible worlds are relegated to minimal publications in the culture or innovation sections.

In times of short messages, of 'likes' on social networks and of the ephemeral, telling stories of transcendental events is displaced by events. It is therefore a good time to study how a 2,000-year-old narrative continues to illuminate the values and authenticity of the human being.

Narrative, chronicles, and social, popular, participatory and educational communication are signs of Latin American identity that transcend because they are relevant and respond to the needs of the environment. Communicating is more than informing, it is encouraging wills to a common action. From this perspective, it is up to professionals in this field to show the different contexts of events for effective freedom of expression.

Therefore, identifying what is good, what is positive and harmonising is necessary to involve many in the search for and implementation of alternatives towards a minimum of governance in Ecuador. Communication must be more and more an epiphany of agreements, encounters and convergences for the development and equity that the country demands.